

Interview guide for Microservices study

Questions

Background:

- What is your background in terms of formal education, training and working experience?
- How many years of experience do you have in Software or Systems Engineering/Development/Design/Architecture?
- What is your current role?
- How much of experience do you have in Microservices (years, projects etc.)?
- What type of Software/System do you currently work with (automotive software, CRM, ERP, Mobile Applications, IoT applications etc.)? Please pick one of your current projects in which you started working in a microservices-based architecture as a reference (the one that you were most involved)?

Main interview:

1. What do you consider as microservice architecture? What defines it and what are you trying to get out of it?
2. Can you briefly describe your journey of architecting, designing and implementing a microservices-based architecture while migrating from a monolith (migration process, transformation etc.)?
3. Can you tell me about different things/properties/aspects that you have considered before starting the design of the microservices architecture that enhanced your work (technical or organizational, internal or external)?
4. What did you do different than the guideline and why? Did you follow the guidelines from (2b) completely, one-to-one?
5. Were there any problems/issues or surprises that came along? (regarding the way about things that you did not consider and afterwards you felt that you should have considered? What, why, how?)
6. What were the costs of facing the different problems and the aspects not considered? (use example from interview)
7. Can you describe a wish list of 3 things you would like to have in retrospective?